

Chemisorption of Oxygen by Charcoal on Treatment with Some Mild Oxidising Agents

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Treatment of charcoal with aqueous solutions of potassium persulphate, potassium bromate, potassium periodate, and potassium nitrate results in chemisorption of an appreciable amount of oxygen, more in original than in degassed samples, leading to the formation of CO_2 -complex, which is completely titratable against alkalis in original, but not so in degassed charcoals. The CO -complex and chemisorbed hydrogen do not undergo any noticeable change as a result of any of the treatments.

It has been shown in previous communications (Puri *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 181; 1960, 37, 171, 401) that interaction of charcoal and halogens in aqueous solution involves hydrolysis of the halogen and chemisorption of oxygen by the charcoal leading to the formation of a complex, capable of evolving carbon dioxide on high-temperature evacuation. It was thought of interest to examine the possibility of chemisorption of oxygen and the formation or extension of the already existing oxygen complexes on charcoal on treatment with some mild oxidising agents. Such investigations are of importance in properly understanding the phenomenon of low-temperature surface oxidation of charcoal as well as the nature of surface-oxygen complexes and alterations in surface characteristics, which it gives rise to.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sugar charcoal and coconut shell charcoal, prepared in the manner described earlier (Puri *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) were used before as well as after degassing at 750° and at 1200° . Nearly saturated aqueous solutions of potassium persulphate (0.35*N*), potassium bromate (2.5*N*), potassium periodate (0.05*N*), and potassium nitrate (0.5*N*) were used for oxidation purposes.

Procedure.—Charcoal (2 g.) was mixed with 200 c.c. of each of the oxidising solutions in 500 c.c. bottles. The suspensions were shaken for about 48 hours after which the bottles were opened under kerosene oil and the gases collected in a graduated cylinder. An aliquot of the gaseous mixture was analysed for its CO_2 , CO , and oxygen contents in an Orsat-Lunge gas analysis apparatus in the usual way. The values were corrected for the amount of these gases normally present in air, as determined by similar analysis of the air in the room.

The charcoal samples were washed thoroughly with distilled water, dried in an oven at 110° , and evacuated at 1200° in a resistance tube furnace, allowing the temperature to rise gradually. The gases evolved were analysed as before (Puri *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

The base-adsorption capacity (b.a.c.) of each charcoal sample before as well as after every treatment was determined as before by shaking 1 g. portions with 100 c.c. of 0.2*N*- $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ solution for about 48 hours and titrating an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid against a standard acid solution in the usual way.

DISCUSSION

Tables I and II show that an appreciable amount of oxygen is chemisorbed by charcoal on treatment with the various oxidising solutions. The original samples take up more oxygen than the evacuated ones, the amount decreasing with increase in the temperature of evacuation. Potassium persulphate brings about maximum surface oxidation of sugar as well as coconut shell charcoal and is followed, in decreasing order, by potassium bromate, potassium periodate, and potassium nitrate. The entire amount of oxygen chemisorbed by charcoal apparently gives rise to CO_2 -complex only, since the values for carbon monoxide and water, evolved before and after the various treatments, are almost identical. The CO -complex and hydrogen are not evidently oxidised to CO_2 -complex and water respectively as there is no noticeable decrease in the amounts of carbon monoxide and hydrogen evolved from any sample of charcoal after respective treatments.

TABLE I
Sugar charcoal.

Description of the sample.	Gases evolved on evacuation at 1200° (mg./g.)				Total oxygen* evolved (mg./g.)	Increase in O_2 content of charcoal (mg./g.)	$\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ neutralised (m.e./100g.)	** CO_2 evolved	
	CO_2 .	CO .	H_2O .	H_2 .					
Before treatment	Original	151	141	125	13	301	..	678	686
	750°-evacuated	Nil	97	65	12	113	..	Nil	Nil
	1200°-evacuated	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	..	Nil	Nil
Treatment with $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$	Original	252	139	125	13	374	73	1163	1145
	750°-evacuated	49	96	65	12	148	35	34	223
	1200°-evacuated	28	Nil	Nil	Nil	20	20	Nil	127
Treatment with KBrO_3	Original	238	139	125	13	364	63	1073	1082
	750°-evacuated	45	97	65	12	145	32	33	205
	1200°-evacuated	22	Nil	Nil	Nil	16	16	Nil	100
Treatment with KIO_4	Original	226	139	125	13	355	54	1017	1027
	750°-evacuated	45	96	65	12	145	32	32	205
	1200°-evacuated	18	Nil	Nil	Nil	13	13	Nil	82
Treatment with KNO_3	Original	206	139	125	13	340	39	944	936
	750°-evacuated	37	97	65	12	140	27	33	168
	1200°-evacuated	15	Nil	Nil	Nil	11	11	Nil	68

* As CO_2 , CO and H_2O .

** On evacuation at 1200°.

No free oxygen or gaseous carbon monoxide appeared to be formed during the reaction; small amounts of gaseous carbon dioxide were, however, formed in case of the original samples only, as shown in Table III. The maximum amount is formed with potassium persulphate and minimum with potassium nitrate.

TABLE II

Coconut shell charcoal.

Description of the sample.	Gases evolved on evacuation at 1200° (mg./g.)				Total oxygen* evolved (mg./g.)	Increase in O ₂ content of charcoal (mg./g.)	Ba(OH) ₂ neutralised (m.e./100g.):	**CO ₂ evolved	
	CO ₂ .	CO.	H ₂ O.	H ₂ .					
Before treatment	Original	70	113	77	13	184	..	312	318
	750°-evacuated	Nil	76	61	12	98	..	Nil	Nil
	1200°-evacuated	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	..	Nil	Nil
Treatment with K ₂ S ₂ O ₈	Original	163	112	77	13	251	67	749	741
	750°-evacuated	46	75	62	12	131	33	47	209
	1200°-evacuated	26	Nil	Nil	Nil	19	19	Nil	118
Treatment with KBrO ₃	Original	148	112	78	13	241	57	668	673
	750°-evacuated	44	75	61	12	129	31	45	200
	1200°-evacuated	21	Nil	Nil	Nil	15	15	Nil	95
Treatment with KIO ₄	Original	143	114	78	12	238	54	656	650
	750°-evacuated	42	76	61	12	128	30	44	191
	1200°-evacuated	18	Nil	Nil	Nil	13	13	Nil	82
Treatment with KNO ₃	Original	117	112	78	13	218	34	526	532
	750°-evacuated	35	75	61	11	123	25	33	159
	1200°-evacuated	14	Nil	Nil	Nil	10	10	Nil	64

* As CO₂, CO and H₂O.

** On evacuation at 1200°.

TABLE III

CO₂ formed by samples of charcoal with oxidising solutions.

Description of the sample.	Type of charcoal.	Amount of CO ₂ evolved (mg./g.) on treatment with			
		K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ .	KBrO ₃ .	KIO ₄ .	KNO ₃ .
Sugar charcoal					
Original		26	24	12	8
750°-evacuated		Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
1200°-evacuated		"	"	"	"
Coconut shell charcoal					
Original		13	13	8	5
750°-evacuated		Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
1200°-evacuated		"	"	"	"

The results reported in Tables I, II, and III show that all the oxidising agents have similar action on each kind of charcoal, the difference being of degree only.

The barium hydroxide values of the various samples before as well as after treatment with different oxidising solutions, expressed as m.e./100g., are included in Tables I and II. The amounts of carbon dioxide evolved from each sample, calculated in the same units, are also given (last column) for easy comparison. There is a considerable increase in the b.a.c. of the original samples of sugar as well as coconut shell charcoal on treatment with oxidising solutions, the maximum value, as expected, being obtained with potassium persulphate. The b.a.c. of sugar charcoal noticeably increases from 686 to 1163 and that of coconut shell charcoal from 312 to 749 m.e./100g. This provides a convenient method of preparing charcoal of high b.a.c. The increase is evidently due to increase in the CO_2 -complex. In fact, it is seen that the amount of barium hydroxide neutralised by the original samples of sugar and coconut shell charcoals, before as well as after every treatment, is almost exactly equivalent to the amount of carbon dioxide evolved from them.

In case of 750° -degassed samples, the barium hydroxide values rise only slightly from zero to a maximum of about 34 and 46 m.e. in sugar and coconut shell charcoals respectively. The amount of barium hydroxide neutralised is, however, considerably less than the amount of carbon dioxide evolved in every treatment.

In case of 1200° -degassed samples, the b.a.c. remains zero even though there is a significant increase in the CO_2 -complex.

These observations show that the CO_2 -complex, formed on degassed samples as a result of treatment with oxidising solutions, is different in nature from that formed on original charcoals and support the conclusion arrived at in previous publications regarding two types of CO_2 -complexes, one of which is completely titratable against alkalis and the other is not. The results also indicate that the view of some of the previous workers (Weller and Young, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 4155; Wilson and Bolam, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1950, **5**, 550) that almost all the chemisorbed oxygen is involved in the sorption of bases from aqueous solution needs further examination and revision as charcoal may have appreciable amount of chemisorbed oxygen, even capable of evolving carbon dioxide, but it may not be titratable against alkalis.